

Community smells

Table 6: Community smells and their relation to social debt factors

Id	Community smells	Factor				
		CD	CSD	COD	STCD	FCD
CS1	<i>Organizational Silo</i> : Teams operate in isolation with no interaction among them [PS3], [PS6–PS9], [PS11–PS17, PS18, PS24, PS27–PS36].	H	H	H	M	H
CS2	<i>Radio Silence</i> : Excessive formality in routine processes delays changes and wastes time [PS4–PS7], PS9, [PS11 – PS18], PS24, [PS27, PS28, PS30 – PS33, PS36, PS41].	H	H	H	H	H
CS3	<i>Bottleneck</i> : Excessive reliance on a single individual [PS6, PS7–PS9, PS11, PS13, PS17, PS18, PS24, PS27, PS32].	M	H	H	M	M
CS4	<i>Black Cloud</i> : A team member who cultivates a negative atmosphere [PS3, PS6–PS9, PS11, PS13, PS24, PS27, PS28, PS30, PS31– PS36].	H	H	M	L	H
CS5	<i>Lone Wolf</i> : Individuals who work in isolation from the rest of the team [PS3, PS6 – PS9, PS11, PS13, PS18, PS24, PS27, PS28, PS30 – PS36].	H	H	H	M	M
CS6	<i>Architecture by Osmosis</i> : Architectural decisions rely on incomplete or poorly managed information shared through informal channels [PS4, PS20, PS27, PS32].	H	H	M	H	M
CS7	<i>Architectural Hood</i> : Occurs when architectural decision-makers are distant from the team, hindering effective collaboration [PS27, PS32].	H	H	H	H	M
CS8	<i>Prima-Donnas</i> : Knowledge is concentrated in a few individuals who avoid sharing it with others [PS3, PS9, PS27].	H	H	M	M	H
CS9	<i>Share Villainy</i> : Arises from poor knowledge-sharing conditions and undervaluing communication as key to productivity [PS27, PS32, PS45].	H	H	M	L	H
CS10	<i>Organizational Skirmish</i> : Refers to cultural, structural, or functional differences that hinder team collaboration and productivity [PS24, PS27, PS31, PS32, PS45].	H	H	H	M	H
CS11	<i>Solution Defiance</i> : Technical solutions are rejected due to interpersonal conflicts, power dynamics, or resistance to change, hindering decision-making [PS27, PS31, PS45].	H	H	M	M	H
CS12	<i>Truck Factor</i> : Critical knowledge is concentrated in few individuals, posing a risk if they are not accessible [PS31, PS32, PS34, PS42].	H	H	H	H	M
CS13	<i>Smelly Developer</i> : Developers affected by organizational silos, lone wolf behaviors, or bottlenecks [PS9, PS17, PS9, PS32].	H	H	M	H	H

CS14	<i>Smelly Quitter</i> : Occurs when a team member abandons their responsibilities without formally notifying the team [PS17].	H	M	H	H	M
CS15	<i>Missing Link</i> : Refers to the absence of effective communication channels among developers [PS3, PS6, PS7, PS14, PS27, PS32, PS38].	H	M	H	H	M
CS16	<i>Class Cognition</i> : Refactoring activities hinder the understanding of modified classes, requiring extra time and effort to grasp their new structure [PS14, PS27].	H	H	M	H	H
CS17	<i>Code Red</i> : Time zone differences that hinder synchronization and coordination among team members [PS2, PS5, PS8, PS15, PS21, PS22, PS24, PS26, PS27, PS45].	M	H	H	M	H
CS18	<i>Cognitive Distance</i> : Physical or cognitive separation that prevents shared understanding within the team [PS2, PS5, PS8, PS9, PS21, PS22, PS25, PS26, PS27].	H	H	M	H	H
CS19	<i>Cookbook Development</i> : Solutions are applied mechanically using templates without assessing relevance, limiting innovation [PS5, PS8, PS27, PS32].	M	H	M	H	H
CS20	<i>DevOps Clashes</i> : Conflicts arise among team members due to divergent goals, practices, work methodologies, or misaligned timelines [PS5, PS8, PS27].	H	H	H	H	H
CS21	<i>Handoff Smell</i> : Arises when developers hand off the product to operations before it is truly complete or mature [PS8].	H	H	M	M	H
CS22	<i>Dispersion</i> : Lack of integration prevents shared vision and team cohesion, leading to duplicated efforts [PS24, PS27].	H	H	H	H	H
CS23	<i>Dissent</i> : Persistent lack of agreement among team members [PS8, PS9, PS27, PS42].	H	H	M	H	H
CS24	<i>Hypercommunity</i> : Intense communication and over-engagement saturate communication channels, undermining team focus [PS27, PS31, PS43, PS45].	H	H	H	M	H
CS25	<i>Excess Informality</i> : Informal communication lacking traceability [PS2, PS5, PS8, PS26].	H	H	H	H	H
CS26	<i>Institutional Isomorphism</i> : Adoption of external practices without contextual analysis [PS5, PS8, PS26].	M	M	H	H	H
CS27	<i>Invisible Architecting</i> : Architectural decisions made in isolation and not communicated [PS4, PS26].	H	M	H	H	M
CS28	<i>Lonesome Architecting</i> : Architectural decisions made by unqualified individuals due to lack of architects [PS4, PS26].	H	H	H	H	H
CS29	<i>Newbie Free-Riding</i> : Inexperienced members lack guidance from seniors [PS12, PS26].	M	M	H	H	H
CS30	<i>Obfuscated Architecting</i> : Lack of shared vision among sub-communities impairs coordination. [PS4, PS26]	H	H	H	H	H

CS31	<i>Power Distance</i> : Occurs when less authoritative members passively expect leaders to handle all decisions and task assignments [PS5, PS7, PS8, PS26].	H	H	M	H	H
CS32	<i>Priggish Members</i> : Arises when some team members are overly cautious, passive, and excessively risk-averse or fearful [PS9, PS26].	H	H	H	M	H
CS33	<i>Unlearning</i> : Occurs when the organization fails to leverage the knowledge and experience of its teams effectively [PS26].	H	H	M	H	H
CS34	<i>Time Warp</i> : Happens when the team overlooks technical advances and relies on outdated methods and structures [PS3, PS8, PS27].	M	H	M	H	H
CS35	<i>Leftover Techie</i> : Emerges when the collaborative network between developers and technicians breaks down, hindering communication [PS3, PS27].	H	M	H	H	H

Acronyms used: Communication factor (CF), Collaboration and social structure (CSF), Coordination (COF), Socio-technical congruence (STCF), and Cultural and organizational factor (COF).